

THE IMPACT OF INCLUSIVE GROWTH ON TRADE BALANCES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research investigates the impact of inclusive growth on trade balances in Nigeria. It computed an inclusive growth index for Nigeria using ten indicators with empirical analysis conducted using principal component analysis from E-view 9 to examine how variables of trade balance impacted on inclusive growth. Error correction mechanism and autoregressive distributed lag model were used to estimate impact of inclusive growth index on trade given the order of integration. The results showed a negative relationship between trade balance variables in enhancing inclusive growth except total labour force which exhibits a positive effect with inclusive growth index in Nigeria. On the whole, all the equations were relevant in explaining the dynamics of inclusive growth in Nigeria due to their relatively high explanatory power of about 51 percent for trade balances equation. Trade balance variables exhibited high speeds of adjustment of 99.05 percent. The paper recommends that government should ensure inclusivity in economic growth and trade balances to achieve its full potentials; and this must be facilitated through creating or encouraging specialization in the export of primary commodities that match imports, capital market efficiency, job creation through a well-managed labour force and ensuring reduction in poverty, inflation, interest rates, etc.

Keywords: Trade balances, exchange rate, Inclusive Growth

Introduction

Background to the Study

Inclusive growth refers to both the pace and pattern of growth, which are considered to be interlinked and therefore, need to be addressed together. The idea that both the pace and pattern of growth are critical for achieving a high, sustainable growth record as well as poverty reduction, is consistent with the findings in The Growth Report: Strategies for Sustained Growth and Inclusive Development (Commission on Growth and Development, 2008).

The balance of trade, commercial balance, or net exports is the difference between the monetary value of a nation's exports and imports over a certain time period (O'Sullivan and Sheffrin, 2003). Sometimes, a distinction is made between a balance of trade for goods versus one for services. The balance of trade measures a flow of exports and imports over a given period of time. The notion of the balance of trade does not mean that exports and imports are "in balance" with each other. If a country exports a greater value than it imports, it has a trade surplus or positive trade balance, and conversely, if a country imports a greater value than it exports, it has a trade deficit or negative trade balance. The balance of trade is one of the key components of a country's gross domestic product (GDP). GDP increases when there is a trade surplus, that is, the total value of goods and services that domestic producers sell abroad exceeds the total value of foreign goods and services that domestic consumers buy.

International integration can promote inclusive growth when workers and firms are able to adjust to enter into growing economic activities and adopt technologies availed through international trade. International openness through trade, trade facilitation and investment have a direct effect on the creation of economic opportunities. Trade is key to economic development because trade facilitates the adaptation and movement of both workers and firms towards sectors with growing demand, and the incorporation of new technologies with the objective of promoting productivity and employment growth of a wide group of workers and firms (World Bank, 2011).

Trade enhances economic growth and is a measured of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria. This indicates that trade is an essential aspect of economic growth. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria was \$166 billion in 2007. The economy has overdependence on the capital-intensive oil sector, which provided 20 percent of GDP, 95 percent of foreign exchange earnings, and about 65 percent of government revenue in 2005. The largely subsistence agricultural sector has not kept up with rapid population growth, and Nigeria, once a large net exporter of food, now imports some of its food products.

There are two likely ways that trade can contribute to inclusive growth. The first is the indirect linkage where trade growth contributes to GDP growth, which in turn can contribute to inclusive growth through employment and consumption multipliers (that is, the trickle-down effect), or a more progressive system of public taxation and service provision through the state. Second is the more direct linkage between trade

and inclusive growth where trade itself benefits poorer segments of society without the intermediation of overall economic growth or the state. This can happen if an economy's exporting sector employs poor workers or if exporting firms are located in poorer regions such as rural areas. Likewise, growth in imports can contribute to inclusive growth if they lead to price reductions in the goods that form a large portion of the poor's consumption basket (example, basic necessities, and medicines) (Hernando *et al.*, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The trends of inclusive growth in Nigeria stood at 0.293 in 1986, increased to 0.355 in 1987, moved to 0.369 in 1991, and then to 0.439 in 1993, with a reduction to 0.325 in 1994. This fluctuation in the index may be attributed to autocratic leadership style prevalent in the economy at the time. With the birth of democracy in 1999, the index of inclusive growth increased to 0.402 in 2001. Banks consolidation policy initiated by the monetary authorities yielded positive results as it improved the index to 0.406 in 2007.

The consequences of mass youth unemployment are evident in the rising number of cases associated with armed robbery, hostage-taking for ransom, illicit drug trafficking and addiction, militancy, including the 'Boko Haram' menace. In related avenue, human development index for ten years period (between 1981 to 1990) rises marginally from 38% to 39%, and again, from 1991 to 2000, 40% to 42%; and between 2001 to 2020, it moved from 43% and then fell to 36%. Also, financial deepening which is the measure of credit to private sector over GDP increases from 6.15 to 6.78 within the period 1981 to 1990, 7.01 to 7.51 in 1991 to 2000, 9.29 in 2001 to 18.96 in 2010 but dropped from there to 18.67 in 2021. More so, trade balances were negative within 1981, 1982 and 1983 with the following figures: -1.816.30, -2.564.10 and -1.401.20, respectively, but improved between 1984 and 1990 with 64% increment to about 64,168.20. From 1991 to 2000, it increased to 96% and between 2001 and 2011, the figure rose to 4.240 million. However, from 2011 to 2021, the figure fell to -3.190 million. This drop in trade balances is attributable to oil theft, Boko Haram, and Niger Delta boys' activities. The attendance social menace and disarticulation experienced in the growth path of the economy, as enumerated above, led to absence of inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Nigeria's trade surplus ballooned to NGN 1,117 billion in December of 2022, from NGN 84 billion in the same month of the previous year. It was the largest monthly trade surplus since December 2012 as exports jumped 36.5% to a six-month high of

NGN 2,353 billion, mainly boosted by shipments of manufactured products (487.5%), solid minerals (92.4%), agricultural goods (42.1%), and crude oil (35.1%). Conversely, imports tumbled 24.7% to a two-year low of NGN 1,236 billion as reduced purchases of agricultural goods (-53.5%), manufactured products (-24.3%), and raw materials (-3.3%) outweighed increases in those of other oil products (+22.7%) and solid minerals (+5.7%). Considering the full year of 2022, the country's trade balance shifted to a surplus of NGN 1,206 billion from a deficit of NGN 1,936 billion a year ago as exports soared 41.7% to NGN 26,797 billion, while imports rose at a slower 22.8% to NGN 25,591 billion.

However, Nigeria's trade surplus shrank slightly to NGN 402 billion in September of 2022, from NGN 449 billion in the same month of the previous year. Exports declined by 11.9% year-on-year to a nine-month low of NGN 1,795 billion, mainly dragged down by lower shipments of crude oil (-6.9%), manufactured products (-79.1%), energy products (-86.4%), and solid minerals (-37.1%). On the other hand, overseas sales grew primarily for other oil products (24%) and agricultural goods (14.4%). Meanwhile, imports slumped 12.4% to a 17-month low of NGN 1,393 billion, as a slump in purchases of other oil products (-80.5%) outweighed increases in imports of agricultural goods (18.4%), raw materials (17.9%), and solid minerals (11.8%).

Nigeria trade balance has been on the decline since 1960 due to the persistent presentation of primary product as export commodity in the international market. The percentage of Nigerian trade balance to GDP in the 1960 stood at -7.68%, but then continued to decline to -0.83% in 1972; it increased marginally to 0.57% in 1973, and further increased to 10.61% in 1974 after which it decreased to its current level of -1.10% in 2021. The reduction in trade balances experienced within this period does not allow for the direct linkage of trade already explained in the previous section to bring about inclusive growth since trade is seen as engine of growth to any economy.

This study therefore, explores the relationship between inclusive growth and trade balances in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of inclusive growth on trade balances in Nigeria.

2.1 Review of Literature

2.1.1 The Concept of inclusive Growth

Inclusive growth refers to both the pace and pattern of growth, which are considered to be interlinked and therefore need to be addressed together. The idea that both the pace and pattern of growth are critical for achieving a high, sustainable growth record, as well as poverty reduction, is consistent with the findings in The Growth Report: Strategies for Sustained Growth and Inclusive Development (Commission on Growth and Development, 2008).

2.1.2 Concept of Trade Balances

The balance of trade, commercial balance, or net exports, is the difference between the monetary value of a nation's exports and imports over a certain time period (O'sullivan and Sheffrin, 2003). Sometimes a distinction is made between a balance of trade for goods versus one for services. The balance of trade measures a flow of exports and imports over a given period of time. The notion of the balance of trade does not mean that exports and imports are "in balance" with each other. If a country exports a greater value than it imports, it has a trade surplus or positive trade balance, and conversely, if a country imports a greater value than it exports, it has a trade deficit or negative trade balance. The balance of trade is one of the key components of a country's gross domestic product (GDP). GDP increases when there is a trade surplus, that is, the total value of goods and services that domestic producers sell abroad exceeds the total value of foreign goods and services that domestic consumers buy.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This study is based on the export-led growth model that was pioneered by Helleiner in 1986. Export-led growth is a policy strategy and a process by which a country aims at accelerating its rate of economic growth by relying upon an expansion of its exports. Its objective is to derive several growth-related benefits from export expansion such as providing employment to its hitherto unemployed and underemployed resources, higher rate of capital accumulation, upgrade of technology through greater imports, and so on. This theory tells us that economic development of a country can be stimulated by export expansion.

The strategy of export-led growth opines that a country tries to specialize in those products in which its factor endowment gives it comparative advantage. International trade stimulates growth of trading countries both by what may be termed "demand motoring" and "supply motoring". This means that international

trade brings into operation a continuous interaction between demand and supply forces and helps them accelerate their growth rates. This strengthens the demand of both traded and domestically consumed products. The resultant increase in production enables the producers to take advantage of the economies of scale, cut costs and prices, and stimulate demand further.

The debate is still inconclusive as to whether a country can rely upon a strategy of export-led growth. International financial institutions like the IMF, the World bank, and the Asian Development Bank, as also several economists like Sachs and Werner, have been forceful advocates of export-led growth. In support of their claim, they cite the cases of those East Asian countries that have successfully pursued this course of action. In contrast, there is an equally strong view that there is no guarantee that the strategy of export-led growth will always succeed; it can be of help only if overall circumstances are favourable to this approach.

2.3 Empirical Literature

2.3.1 Studies on inclusive Growth and Trade Balances

Bacchetta, Cerra, Piermartini, and Smeets (2021) in their work on Trade and Inclusive Growth, examined the claims that the rise in inequality in many countries can be attributed to the concurrent rise in trade competition, especially from EMEs like China, spurring trade tensions and protectionist measures. The paper surveyed the literature on the relationship between international trade and inclusive growth and further investigated the conflicting literature showing the aggregate benefits of trade versus the adverse and persistent impact of trade, especially import competition, on specific industries and local communities. The paper then reviewed the evidence for using trade policies and other complementary policies for adjustment and compensation to those groups adversely affected by trade.

Rasool, Adil and Tarique (2022) examined the drivers of inclusive growth in India using annual data from 1981 to 2015. The study employs the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and the error correction method (ECM) to investigate the long-run and short-run relationship between inclusive growth and its determinants. The bounds test findings confirm the cointegrating relationship among variables. The ARDL estimates suggest that growth in initial income, government expenditure, human development, investment and financial development fosters inclusive growth; while inflation and population growth dampen it. The results also imply that increasing trade openness and foreign direct investment would not be beneficial for India in terms of growth inclusiveness.

Sanni, Musa and Sani (2019) examined current account balance and economic growth in Nigeria: an empirical investigation. This study focused on the relationship between current account balance and economic growth in Nigeria. Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds Testing methodology was employed to investigate the relationship using annual data spanning from 1970 – 2016. The study found a long-run relationship between the current account balance, the real gross domestic product (GDP) growth, and bilateral real exchange rate in Nigeria. The positive relationship between real GDP growth and the current account balance implies that increase in real GDP growth would lead to an improvement in the current account balance. However, the study found a negative relationship between real exchange rate and current account balance. Depreciation in the exchange rate would lead to the deterioration in the current account balance. This latter result has implications for the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) exchange rate management strategy. Specifically, maintaining a stable exchange rate should continue to be a priority for the CBN given the debilitating effect of a depreciating exchange rate on the current account, and by extension, economic growth.

Ikpesu, Olusegun and Dakare (2019) in their study on growth effect of trade and investment in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries, examined the role of trade and investment in the growth process in the SSA using trade openness (% of GDP), export (% of GDP) and import (% of GDP) as measures of trade. They embrace an ideographic perspective that allows methodology and design that are sensitive to the nature of the study by deploying panel corrected standard error (PCSE). The research outcomes reveal that domestic trade investment and import affect growth in the region positively, while export affects growth negatively. A possible reason for this is the nature of export of sub-Saharan African economies which are mostly affected by price volatility in the global market among other factors such as low prices, vagaries of weather, etc.

Oloyede, Osabuohien and Ejemeyovwi (2021) research on trade openness and economic growth in Africa's regional economic communities: empirical evidence from ECOWAS and SADC, analyses the relationship among trade openness and macroeconomic outlook of Africa's regional economic communities (RECs), focusing on the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and Southern African Development Community (SADC). The study applied the Pooled OLS, Fixed and Random Effects techniques of estimation, and the Durbin-Wu Hausman test for endogeneity to categorized secondary data from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI) and the United Nations Conference on Trade

and Development (UNCTAD) databases. The data sets were classified into three segments for comparative analysis, comprising the total, ECOWAS, and SADC datasets. The results show a positive but insignificant nexus between economic growth rate and trade openness in both the combined simulated ECOWAS and SADC and the individual REC. The results emphasize that the government and other relevant stakeholders should ensure policies are enacted and enforced to transmit the experienced economic growth into substantial trade gains and further trade openness in ECOWAS and SADC.

Deimante, Garsviene and Matuzeviciute (2020) investigated how trade openness affects economic growth in developing countries, with a focus on sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). They used a dynamic growth model with data from 42 SSA countries covering 1980 to 2012, and employed the Pooled Mean Group estimation technique, which is appropriate for drawing conclusions from dynamic heterogeneous panels by considering long-run equilibrium relations. The empirical evidence indicates that a trade threshold exists below which greater trade openness has beneficial effects on economic growth, and above which the trade effect on growth declines. The evidence also indicates an inverted U-curve (Laffer curve of trade) response, robust to changes in trade openness measures and to alternative model specifications, suggesting the non-fragility of the linkage between economic growth and trade openness for sub-Saharan countries.

Sandri, Alshyab and Ghazo (2016) investigated trade in goods and services and its effect on economic growth – the case of Jordan. The study empirically showed the specific growth contribution of trade in goods and services in Jordan for the period 1980-2014. The model was estimated using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares approach, which corrects for endogeneity of data and serial correlation. The results of the estimated regression are in tune with the economic theory. In particular, it emerges that trade in goods has a negative effect on GDP in Jordan, whereas trade in services positively affects economic performance.

3.1 Method

To achieve the stated objective, an inclusive growth index was computed using the theoretical model of Paramasivan, Mani and Utpal (2014) as well as Mckinley (2010) in identifying and selecting the indicators that constitute the index, and the data for the identified inclusive growth variables which include life expectancy, control of corruption, GDP per capita, unemployment, government expenditure on education, electric power consumption, number of bank branches, credit to SME's, financial

sector efficiency and personal income share in National income (GDP) to compute an inclusive growth index by summing up to derive a single value using principal component analysis from E-view 9 approach in generating the Inclusive Growth Index for Nigeria

Thus:

$$IGI_t = \frac{LEXP + CONCOR + GDPPC + EMP + GOVEXE + EPC + NBB + CTS + FSE + PIS}{IGI_{t-1}}$$

With data from the World Bank (2021) indicators, taking 1981 as the base year, data for the ten variables listed was collected; summed up for the individual years studied and divided by the based year data by using principal component analysis from E-view 9. The computation shows that the IGI_{1981} (the base year) is -2.23, and the index lies between 0 and 1. So if the value is close to zero, then growth is not inclusive; but the closer the value to one, the more inclusive growth is.

3.1.1 Model Specification:

Following the theories and the empirical literature reviewed, the model specification for this study is:

3.1.1.1 Inclusive Growth Index (IGI) and Trade Balances Model is specified as:

$$IGI = F(\text{Trade balances}) \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

where IGI is inclusive growth index, Equation 3.1 becomes Equation 3.2 represented as follows:

$$IGI = f(\text{OPEN, BOP, FDI, EXCHR, RES, INTR, INFL, MC, TLF}) \quad \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Where:

OPEN – Openness

BOP – Balance of Payments

FDI – Foreign Direct investment

EXCHR – Exchange Rate

RES – Reserve

INTR – Interest Rate

INFL – Inflation Rate

MC – Capital Market

TFL – Total Labour Force

The econometric form of the Equation 3.13 now becomes:

$$IGI_t = a_0 + a_1 \text{OPEN}_t + a_2 \text{BOP}_t + a_3 \text{FDI}_t + a_4 \text{EXCHR}_t + a_5 \text{RES}_t + a_6 \text{INTR}_t + a_7 \text{INFL}_t + a_8 \text{MC}_t + a_9 \text{TLF}_t + V \quad \text{Equation 3.3}$$

where; a_0 is the constant of regression ($a_0 \neq 0$) a_0 to a_9 are the parameter estimates of

the explanatory variables to capture their direction and magnitude of effect on inclusive growth, and v is the stochastic term.

The a priori expectation is that $a_1 > 0$; $a_2 > 0$; $a_3 > 0$; $a_4 < 0$; $a_5 > 0$; $a_6 < 0$; $a_7 < 0$; $a_8 > 0$; $a_9 > 0$.

3.1.3 Model Estimation Procedure

The ADF and PP unit root test was adopted to determine the order of integration, while the causality test seeks to detect the direction of causality. Co-integration test was used to determine the existence of long-run equilibrium relationship (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

If the order of integration of the time series variables are of order one (i.e., $I(1)$), then Johansen co-integration test is suitable; but if the order of integration is a combination of order zero and one (i.e., $I(0)$ and $I(1)$), ARDL-bounds co-integration test procedure is suitable. This study used both the Johansen and ARDL tests for co-integration. ARDL was used for inclusive growth, and trade and Error correction mechanism was used for the equation. The analytical software of the study is E-Views 9 software.

4.1 Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Long Run Coefficient of Inclusive Growth Index and Trade Balances Equation Results

Table 4.1a: Long run coefficients of inclusive growth and trade balance equation
Dependent variable: IGI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BOP	-0.095859	0.112126	-0.854927	0.4038
EXCHR	-0.008165	0.007450	-1.095998	0.2875
FDI	-0.336677	0.329314	-1.022360	0.3202
INFLA	-0.015831	0.026299	-0.601944	0.5547
INTR	-0.433571	0.173988	-2.491961	0.0227
MC	-0.000086	0.000105	-0.825658	0.4198
OPEN	-2.263454	3.367387	-0.672169	0.5100
RES	-0.006024	0.003429	-1.756550	0.0960
TLF	0.000000	0.000000	3.693305	0.0017
C	3.948052	2.246347	1.757543	0.0958

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023).

The long-run equation of Inclusive Growth Index and trade balances equation is reported in Table 4.1a. According to the ARDL long-run estimates, the relationship between inclusive growth index (IGI) and EXCHR is negative and in line with theoretical expectation, showing that an increase in EXCHR by 1% will lead to -0.008% reduction in IGI in the long-run *ceteris paribus*. Also, an increase in inflation rate by 1% will lead to -0.02% reduction in IGI. This is in line with *a priori* expectation, meaning that inflation has a devastating effect on IGI in the long run. Moreso, the relationship between INTR and IGI is negative, placing it also in line with theoretical expectation. Therefore, a 1% increase in INTR will reduce IGI by -0.43% in the long run.

Similarly, there exist a positive but significant relationship between TLF and IGI. This result is in line with *a priori* expectation; therefore, an increase in TLF will reduce IGI by 0.0001%. This result signifies that during the period under review, increases in the trade variables did not have any significant impact on inclusive growth (IGI).

4.2.4.4 Short Run Coefficients of Inclusive Growth Index and Trade Balances Equation

Table 4.1b: Short run coefficients of inclusive growth index and trade balances result Dependent variable IGI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IGI(-1))	-0.241433	0.219811	-1.098364	0.2865
D(BOP)	0.014601	0.013934	1.047853	0.3086
D(BOP(-1))	0.020243	0.014034	1.442449	0.1664
D(EXCHR)	-0.002545	0.002705	-0.940861	0.3592
D(FDI)	0.094013	0.097172	0.967493	0.3461
D(FDI(-1))	0.145025	0.074228	1.953781	0.0664
D(INFLA)	0.014510	0.006234	2.327546	0.0318
D(INFLA(-1))	0.012203	0.006276	1.944488	0.0676
D(INTR)	-0.135150	0.030635	-4.411559	0.0003
D(MC)	0.000010	0.000024	0.393450	0.6986
D(MC(-1))	-0.000044	0.000025	-1.786929	0.0908
D(OPEN)	0.722282	0.935641	0.771965	0.4502
D(OPEN(-1))	1.875500	1.143558	1.640056	0.1184
D(RES)	-0.001878	0.000815	-2.305022	0.0333

D(TLF)	0.000000	0.000000	3.330508	0.0037
CointEq(-1)	-0.511714	0.144028	-2.164255	0.0441
Cointeq = IGI - (-0.0959*BOP -0.0082*EXCHR -0.3367*FDI -0.0158*INFLA				
-0.4336*INTR -0.0001*MC -2.2635*OPEN -0.0060*RES + 0.0000*TLF +3.9481)				
R-squared	0.990575	Mean dependent var	0.108218	
Adjusted R-squared	0.979579	S.D. dependent var	2.084499	
S.E. of regression	0.297880	Akaike info criterion	0.717242	
Sum squared resid	1.597188	Schwarz criterion	1.646126	
Log likelihood	7.655150	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.053098	
F-statistic	90.08494	Durbin-Watson stat	2.142881	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model

Source: Researcher 's Computation (2023).

Table 4.1b above reports the short-run dynamics result of inclusive growth index and trade balances equation. From the table, there exist a positive relationship between balance of payments (BOP) and inclusive growth index (IGI) in both current and one period lag; this implies that a unit change in BOP will lead to 0.014% and 0.020% increase in IGI in both periods. This result is in line with *a priori* expectation. Also, the coefficient of exchange rate (EXCHR) shows a negative relationship with IGI, and this implies that a 1% increase in EXCHR will result in 0.002% reduction in IGI. This result is in line with *a priori* expectation, as the negative effect of EXCHR causes foreign debt whose burden undermines naira exchange rate in the short run.

The coefficient of foreign direct investment (FDI) is positively related to IGI at both current and a period lag; meaning that a unit change in FDI will result in 0,094 and 0.145% increases in IGI. This result is in conformity with *a priori* expectation, showing that FDI increases capital and net inflow that will in turn improve economic growth and development *ceteris paribus*. Also, the coefficient of inflation rate (INFLA) is positively and significantly related to IGI at current period and insignificant at one period lag; this implies that a 1% increase in INFLA will lead to 0.0145 and 0.0122% increases in IGI at both periods. This is in contravention with theoretical expectation. Moreso, the sign and magnitude of interest rate (INTR)

shows that there exists a negative and significant relationship between INTR and IGI; therefore, a unit change in INTR will lead to a 0.135% decrease in IGI. The coefficient of capital market (MC) shows positive and negative relationship with IGI in both current and one period lag and this suggests that 1% increase in MC will result in 0.0001% decrease in the current period, and 0.00044% increase after one period lag. The sign and magnitude of openness (OPEN) shows a positive relationship with IGI; this therefore implies that a unit change in OPEN will lead to 0.722% and 1.875% decrease in IGI. This result is in line with the theoretical expectation suggesting that *ceteris paribus*, the degree of openness of Nigeria's economy in the period under study, brings about an improvement in the nation's balance of payments, thereby creating a balance of trade surplus in the short-run. On the contrary, the coefficient of reserve (RES) shows a negative but significant relationship with IGI, meaning that 1% increase in reserve (RES) will result in 0.0018% increase in IGI. The result is in contravention with *a priori* expectation. Finally, the sign and magnitude of total labour force (TLF) shows that there is a positive and significant relationship with IGI, showing that total labour force TLF impacts IGI positively.

The Error correction mechanism (ECM) has the correct sign and size. The ECM coefficient of -0.511714 indicates that it takes about 51 percent for the short run disequilibrium to adjust to the long-run equilibrium within the year. The t-statistic of -2.164255 shows that the error correction term is statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance.

R-squared value of 0.990575 and the value of R-squared adjusted of 0.979579 indicate that about 99 percent of variation in the IGI is explained by current and one period lag of openness, balance of payments, foreign direct investment, reserve, exchange rate, interest rate, capital market, total labour force and inflation rate, and about 1 percent was unexplained which may be accounted for by other factors not included in the model. The F-statistic of about 90.08 shows that all the variables in the inclusive growth model are together as a group and it is statistically significant, which means that the model has a good fit. The Durbin-Watson (D-W) statistic of 2.14 indicates no autocorrelation in the model, therefore, the results can be used for economic forecast and economic policy.

4.2 Discussion

The long-run and short-run equations of inclusive growth index and trade balances equation showed a negative relationship between trade balances variables - balance

of payments, foreign direct investment, openness, capital market and reserve, and inclusive growth. This is in contravention to theoretical expectation except total labour force, exchange rate, inflation rate, and interest rate, which is in line with *a priori* expectation. The contraventions of the above variables indicate that the null hypothesis will be rejected, showing that inclusive growth does not significantly impact trade balances in the period under review.

Moreso, positive, negative and significant relationships were found between balance of payments, openness, foreign direct investment, total labour force and inflation rate in both long and short-run period. This is in line with views of Sandri, Alshyab and Ghazo (2016), Deimante Garsviene and Matuzeviciute (2020), Bacchetta, Cerra, Piermartini, and Smeets (2021) who studied the relationship between international trade and inclusive growth. It examines claims that the rise in inequality in many countries can be attributed to the concurrent rise in trade competition, especially from EMEs like China, spurring trade tensions and protectionist measures. Their study further investigated the conflicting literature showing the aggregate benefits of trade versus the adverse and persistent impact of trade, especially import competition on specific industries and local communities. Their study, therefore, reviews the evidence for using trade policies and other complementary policies for adjustment and compensation to those groups adversely affected by trade.

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of inclusive growth on trade balances in Nigeria. The autoregressive distributive lag (ARDL) and co-integration test techniques were used to determine the long-run and short-run equilibrium relationship among the variables, and the principal component analysis. E-view 9 was used to generate inclusive growth index to test for the impact of inclusive growth index on trade balances and economic development in Nigeria. The bound test result shows that a long-run relationship exists among the variables in the estimated equations. The results of the volatility in inclusive growth index, exchange rate and other identified trade balances in Nigeria (using the autoregressive distributive lag model techniques) revealed a positive, negative and insignificant relationship between the responsiveness of inclusive growth and the various components of trade balances such as openness, foreign direct investment, balance of payments, reserve, interest rate, inflation rate, capital market, total labour force and economic development in both short-run and long-run period. It was revealed from the findings that economic development response negatively to fluctuation in inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Interest rate, inflation rate, inclusive growth index, and poverty were found to exhibit negative responses on economic development in Nigeria within the period under review. Also, coefficient of relationship between inclusive growth index and trade balances showed negative response, meaning that inclusive growth did not enhance trade balances during the period under study.

Predicated on the above, it is recommended that government create job opportunities for teeming populace through fostering entrepreneurial spirit, development of basic skills, target support for job creation in sectors like agriculture, and so on. The government should consciously direct policy actions towards the enhancement of inclusivity in economic growth and trade balances in order to improve economic growth in Nigeria. This must be facilitated through creating appropriate and enabling environment for proper take-off and enhancement of inclusive growth, encourage specialization in the export of primary commodities that match imports, capital market efficiency, job creation through a well-managed labour force; and ensure reduction in poverty, inflation and interest rates all to enhance inclusivity in economic growth, which will in turn enhance balances trade policy and economic growth in Nigeria.

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